

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ML AND DL MODELS FOR GENDER PREDICTION IN DEVANAGARI SCRIPT

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Abstract

This study investigates the feasibility of identifying gender via personal names written in the Devanagari script. While extensive research exists for languages like English, Russian, and Brazilian, little attention has been given to low-resource language like Nepali. This study addresses this gap, aiming to enhance gender classification in Nepali names. We compare traditional machine learning algorithms along with advanced contextualized transformer architectures like variants of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) specifically fine-tuned for detecting gender among individuals with Nepali names. Our experiments aim at exploring how effectively these techniques capture linguistic nuances unique to the Nepali language and assess their overall performance in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score metrics. Both experiments reveal superior performance by the BERT variants DeBERTa and DistilBERT, demonstrating the merits of advanced NLP techniques for gender classification in Nepali. The study also shows that the additional encoding of name endings (last character of a name) improve the performance of traditional ML algorithms by 10%. Through this work, we contribute to gender classification methodologies tailored specifically for the linguistic nuances of the Nepali language.

1 INTRODUCTION

Gender detection has been a captivating research area within AI. Detecting gender is a multifaceted process, often involving innovative approaches using Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Computer Vision (CV). Accurate gender identification in domains like newspapers, social sites, articles, etc provides valuable insights into existing biases, representation, and diversity [1, 2]. Gender classification is a complex task that requires careful consideration of cultural, social and individual factors. Accurate gender detection helps create targeted advertisements, gives users personalized content, makes customer support faster, and assists market researchers in understanding audience segments. Inclusive and unbiased AI services require continuous improvements in reliable gender detection.

Many research has been conducted utilizing NLP [3, 4, 5], CV [6, 7] for gender detection task. There are commercial applications too which can predict gender based on the name [8, 9, 10]. These commercial applications primarily rely on dictionaries to predict the gender and are not freely accessible for the community. Moreover, these commercial applications do not have much information for low resources language.

Although there has been many approach to detect the gender using the name for languages like English, Russian, Brazilian [3, 4, 5], very little or no has been research done for low resource language like Nepali Name in Nepali script. The unique linguistic characteristics and cultural nuances of low-resource languages like Nepali remain largely unexplored in the context of gender prediction. In this paper, we applied a range of machine learning and deep learning algorithms to analyze 502,468 Nepali names written in the Nepali script for gender detection. For the gender classification task of Nepali names, we trained traditional ML

algorithms, including Random Forest, K Neighbours Classifier, Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, LDA, QDA, SVM, gradient boosting, and BERT-based classifiers like DistilBERT and DeBERTa, on a dataset comprising Nepali names written in the Nepali script, split into an 80:20 train-test ratio.

2 RELATED WORKS

Computer Vision applications mainly use facial features [11, 12, 13] to detect the gender of a person. The use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and other advanced algorithms allows for robust gender classification based on facial attributes and patterns [14].

Identifying the gender of a person based on their name is a common NLP task and can be accomplished using techniques like gender pronoun usage, language models and machine learning, gender specific name etc.

In [15] Goswami et al. conducted a gender detection experiment on 9,660 gender-labeled blog posts from blogger.com. Their model, incorporating features such as slang word statistics and sentence length, achieved an impressive accuracy of 89.3%.

Vashisth and Meehan [16] delved into gender inference using NLP techniques, including bag of words, word embedding, logistic regression, SVM, and Naive Bayes, using Twitter data.

In the paper [4] the authors used a method utilizing three types of features (word endings, character n-grams and dictionary of names) combined within a linear supervised model to detect the gender by full name for Russian language. The paper shows that the proposed strategy is highly successful as accuracy upto 96% is achieved.

Similarly, [5] implemented several ML algorithms to detect gender of a name for Brazilian language. According to [5] some models accurately predict gender in more than 95% of the cases. The paper also show that recurrent models overcome the feedforward models in the binary classification of gender.

In [3], Yifan Hu et. al. proposed a high accuracy character level algorithm to detect the gender of a person using name. The paper also show that using last name in addition to the first name improve the performance of the model.

3 DATASET AND PREPROCESSING

3.1 Nepali Names

Nepali names, unlike English names, present distinctive challenges for machine learning algorithms due to their unique linguistic and cultural attributes. For example, when transliterating the English name "Albert Einstein" into Nepali, it becomes एल्बर्ट आइन्स्टाइन. The Devanagari script introduces different characters, illustrating the complexities that machine learning algorithms must navigate when handling Nepali names.

Furthermore, Nepali names often exhibit gender-specific associations based on certain characters at the end. For instance, names ending with "ा" (aa), "ी" (ii), "ू" (uu) or "या" (yaa) are commonly linked to feminine gender. Examples include "सीता" (Sita), "मन्जु" (Manju) and "रजनी" (Rajni).

The gender association can be emphasized through the presence or absence of specific characters. For instance, "Ishani" (ईशानी) is feminine, while "Ishan" (ईशान) is masculine, showcasing how the addition or removal of characters conveys gender-specific information in Nepali names.

3.2 Dataset

The experimental dataset comprises a total of 502,468 Nepali names, with 235,870 marked as male and 266,598 as female. The dataset was acquired through web scraping from the official website of Election Commission, Nepal[17].

The preprocessing of the scraped data involved several steps to ensure its quality and reliability. First, faulty names were systematically eliminated from the dataset. Entries containing gibberish elements such as hyphens (-), periods (.), or random numbers were identified and removed. Names with obvious mistakes that were easily observable were excluded from the dataset. It's essential to note that the original dataset remained unaltered for reasons unrelated to the aforementioned issues.

To address the possibility of a single name being associated with both genders, a frequency-based approach was implemented to assign labels. In instances where a name had entries for both male and female genders, the gender label was determined based on the higher count. This approach aimed to enhance the accuracy and consistency of gender labeling within the dataset, acknowledging the potential ambiguity of certain names across genders.

Table 1 presents a sample data of the overall dataset. The table includes the first names in Nepali script along with the corresponding counts of females and males, as well as the gender classification.

Table 1: Sample Data

First Name	#Female	#Male	Gender
रितेन्द्रकुमार	0	1	1
नित्रकला	1	0	0
बागुर	0	3	1
बेलसपुरा	26	0	0
पुलहोवा	0	1	1

The figure 1 visually represents the gender distribution within the dataset, where '0' corresponds to female names and '1' corresponds to male names. Notably, the bar graph reveals that the number of occurrences for female names (266,598) exceeds that of male names (235,870).

Figure 1: Gender Distribution of Names

Figure 2 depicts a histogram illustrating the frequency distribution of names based on their respective lengths. The histogram exhibits a right-skewed distribution. As observed in the histogram, a significant proportion of names predominantly falls within the length range of 3 to 11 characters. Moreover, there are very few names with the name length greater than 14.

Figure 2: Distribution of Name Lengths

3.3 Tokenization

Tokenization in Natural Language Processing (NLP) is the process of breaking down a text into smaller units known as tokens. Typically, in NLP tasks, texts are broken down into words. However, for this paper, names are tokenized by breaking them into individual characters, as names are often comprised of single words.

After tokenization, the CountVectorizer is employed for feature extraction. The CountVectorizer from scikit-learn is utilized to convert the tokenized names into a numerical format suitable for machine learning models. This transformation allows us to represent each name as a numerical vector, capturing the relationships between individual characters and providing a foundation for gender classification.

3.4 Class Weights

As the dataset is imbalanced, we utilize class weights when finetuning pretrained models. Class weights enable adjusting the loss computation to penalize false predictions for minority classes more heavily compared to majority class. Weight for the majority female name is 0.4691 and weight for the minority male name is 0.5309. This configuration encourages the model to maintain a delicate equilibrium balancing the learning rates for each class, ultimately benefiting the final performance on the challenging imbalanced dataset.

4 MODELS FOR GENDER DETECTION

Traditional ML algorithms like Random Forest, K Neighbours Classifier, Decision Trees, Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, LDA, QDA, SVM, gradient boosting along with BERT based classifier like DistilBERT and DeBERTa were trained and evaluated for the task. There were 2 types of method based on input of the traditional ML models. These two types of method were trained separately based on inputs and their result is compared.

- **Experiment 1:** Only first name was given as input to model.
- **Experiment 2:** First name along with additional encoding for name endings was given as input to

model. For instance, if the first name is एलिशा, then additional encoding for name endings i.e "ा" (ii) is also added to first name as input. So, the input for this experiment becomes एलिशा + "ा".

Figure 3 illustrates the comprehensive flow of Experiment 1 involving traditional ML algorithms. The process begins with tokenizing the input at the character level, followed by vectorization. Subsequently, the model is trained based on the chosen algorithm, leading to the classification of the input name.

Figure 3: Experiment 1 Flow Diagram

Figure 4 illustrates flow of Experiment 2. It is similar to the Experiment 1 except additional encoding is added for the name endings. The input is tokenized at the character level, followed by vectorization. Then, the input is forwarded to the chosen ML model, leading to the classification of the input name.

Figure 4: Experiment 2 Flow Diagram

4.1 Decision Tree

Decision tree, a widely used supervised learning method for tackling classification and regression problems, operates as a structured classifier. In this framework, internal nodes correspond to features of a dataset, branches represent the decision-making process, and each leaf node indicates the classification result. This approach involves splitting datasets into tree-like structures to facilitate decision-making [18]. For our problem, we employed a Decision Tree as a classifier. Our decision tree model, designed to predict the gender of a given name, utilizes the Gini impurity function. The entire training set serves as the root, and the character-level vector is recursively distributed based on gender.

4.2 Random Forest

Random forests are a group of methods that involve creating an ensemble (or forest) of decision trees. These trees are developed using a randomized version of the tree induction algorithm. We implemented a Random Forest classifier with the parameter `n_estimators` set to 100, specifying the number of trees in the forest. Furthermore, we employed the Gini impurity function to evaluate the quality of splits within each decision tree.

4.3 LDA and QDA

Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA) are two fundamental classification methods in statistical and probabilistic learning [19]. LDA assumes that features are normally distributed and have a common covariance matrix for each class. It seeks a linear combination of features to maximize the separation between class means while minimizing within-class

spread. On the other hand, QDA relaxes the assumption of a common covariance matrix, allowing each class to have its covariance structure.

4.4 Naive Bayes

The Naive Bayes Classifier relies on the Bayesian theorem and is well-suited for scenarios with high-dimensional inputs. Despite its simplicity, Naive Bayes has demonstrated effectiveness, often outperforming more intricate classification methods [20].

4.5 K Neighbors Classifier

It involves categorizing new examples based on the predominant category assignment of their closest counterparts within a reference dataset. We used K-nearest neighbors for binary classification. The classifier had 5 neighbors and used a simple weight function.

4.6 Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine (SVM) stands as a widely adopted Supervised Learning algorithm applied to both classification and regression tasks, with a primary focus on Classification problems in Machine Learning. The objective of the SVM algorithm is to identify the optimal line or decision boundary, effectively classifying n-dimensional space to assign new data points to their respective categories. The concept of a hyperplane is central to achieving the best decision [18].

4.7 Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a classification techniques which is used to identify the most suitable model to establish a relationship between the dependent and independent variables. In this study, the logistic regression classifier was implemented with a stopping criteria tolerance of 0.0001 and norm-L2 in the penalization.

4.8 Gradient Boosting

Gradient Boosting Classifier is a machine learning algorithm used for classification tasks. It is a part of the ensemble learning methods and is particularly powerful for building robust and accurate predictive models. The algorithm builds an ensemble of weak learners, typically decision trees, and combines them to create a strong predictive model.

4.9 DeBERTa and DistilBERT

4.9.1 DeBERTa

DeBERTa (Decoding-enhanced BERT with Disentangled Attention) is a Transformer-based neural language model that aims to improve the BERT and RoBERTa models. It introduces two novel techniques Disentangled Attention which enhances the model's ability to capture intricate relationships between tokens by reducing attention entanglement, and Enhanced Mask Decoder which refines the

decoding mechanism for improved language understanding. These mechanisms collectively contribute to DeBERTa’s enhanced performance in various natural language processing tasks [21].

4.9.2 DistilBERT

DistilBERT is a compressed version of BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers), designed for improved computational efficiency while maintaining considerable performance. Knowledge distillation is performed during the pre-training phase to reduce the size of a larger BERT model by 40%. Developed by Hugging Face, DistilBERT uses knowledge distillation, learning from the larger BERT model as its teacher. With a reduced number of layers and parameters, DistilBERT achieves a streamlined architecture, making it suitable for resource-constrained environments [22, 23].

5 PERFORMANCE METRICS

To evaluate the performance of the trained model we are using 4 performance metrics namely Accuracy, Recall, Precision and F1 Score.

5.1 Accuracy

Accuracy is a number between 0 and 1. It measures the overall correctness of a model. It is calculated as the ratio of correctly predicted instances (sum of correct value) to the total samples measured.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{Total Predictions}} \times 100\%$$

5.2 Recall

Recall also known as sensitivity is the percentage of positive samples that were correctly labelled.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \times 100\%$$

5.3 Precision

Precision also known as positive predictive value is the percentage of samples that were correctly labelled as "positive" compared to all the samples that were labelled as "positive".

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \times 100\%$$

5.4 F1 Score

F1 scores is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. It considers both precision and recall in a single value.

$$\text{F1 Score} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

In the above formulas,

- **True Positives (TP)** represent the instances that are correctly labeled as positives by the model.

- **False Negatives (FN)** represent the instances that are incorrectly labeled as negatives by the model.
- **True Negatives (TN)** represent the instances that are correctly labeled as negatives by the model.
- Lastly, **False Positives (FP)** represent the instances that are incorrectly labeled as positive by the model.

6 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As we considered gender classification as a binary classification task, the input to the model was the first name and output was gender. All the models were trained on Google colab. For traditional ML models PyCaret was used and for training DeBERTa and DistilBERT PyTorch was used. For ML models default parameters as provided by the PyCaret implementation was used except for cross validation where 5 fold cross validation is used. For Deep Learning models following parameters were used.

- Train Size = 64, Valid Size = 32
- Epochs = 5, Learning Rate = 0.00001
- Loss = BCELoss, Optimizer = Adam
- Max length of input = 15
- weight decay=0.01

6.1 Results for Experiment 1

Table 2 displays the results obtained from Experiment 1, in which solely the given name served as input. Among the BERT variants examined, DeBERTa and DistilBERT surpassed conventional machine learning algorithms in performance. Notably, DeBERTa achieved the greatest accuracy, reaching 0.8720, whereas DistilBERT trailed closely behind. Regarding classical techniques, Random Forest led the pack with an accuracy measure of 0.7682, whilst Quadratic Discriminant Analysis (QDA) and Naive Bayes delivered inferior results comparable to merely making a random selection.

Table 2: Performance comparison of the algorithms on Experiment 1

Model Name	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1
DeBERTa	0.8720	0.8710	0.8719	0.8714
DistilBERT	0.8699	0.8695	0.8694	0.8695
Random Forest	0.7682	0.7414	0.7588	0.7500
K Neighbors	0.7380	0.6860	0.7371	0.7107
Gradient Boosting	0.7276	0.6967	0.7153	0.7058
Decision Tree	0.7231	0.6754	0.7176	0.6958
Logistic Regression	0.7126	0.6830	0.6978	0.6903
SVM	0.7126	0.6961	0.6935	0.6942
LDA	0.7123	0.6843	0.6969	0.6906
Naive Bayes	0.5368	0.6200	0.5628	0.4784
QDA	0.5277	0.4981	0.6025	0.3943

6.2 Results for Experiment 2

Table 3 displays the results obtained from Experiment 2, in which first name along with additional encoding for name endings was provided as input. Adding additional encoding result in better performance for traditional ML algorithm as around 10% in accuracy is seen for traditional ML algorithm in experiment 2. Similarly to experiment 1, Random Forest performed better in the traditional ML group with accuracy of 0.8525. For BERT variants, we did not see an improvement in performance when additional encoding is used compared to experiment 1 as the accuracy reached to 0.8705 for DeBERTa and 0.8715 for DistilBERT. This shows that the additional encoding of name endings did not help in the performance of BERT variants.

Table 3: Performance comparison of the algorithms on Experiment 1

Model Name	Accuracy	Recall	Precision	F1
DistilBERT	0.8714	0.8702	0.8715	0.8707
DeBERTa	0.8705	0.8701	0.8701	0.8701
Random Forest	0.8525	0.8516	0.8369	0.8442
K Neighbors	0.8437	0.8193	0.8431	0.8310
Logistic Regression	0.8283	0.8405	0.8027	0.8211
Gradient Boosting	0.8283	0.8596	0.7921	0.8245
LDA	0.8263	0.8526	0.7928	0.8216
SVM	0.8250	0.8589	0.7873	0.8216
Decision Tree	0.8112	0.7916	0.8030	0.7973
Naive Bayes	0.6724	0.3726	0.8404	0.5100
QDA	0.6156	0.3988	0.7898	0.4487

7 LIMITATION AND FUTURE WORK

While conducting the study, several opportunities for extending and deepening the exploration emerged. However, certain limitations were identified, which can be investigated further:

- Like name endings, middle name play important role in gender classification for Nepali name. For example name with middle name like **कुमार, राज, लाल, प्रसाद, बहादुर,** etc is considered masculine whereas name with middle name like **देवी, कुमारी, माया,** etc is considered feminine names. To improve the performance of gender classification model further investigation on the importance of middle name could be considered.
- N-grams of the name endings could also be beneficial along with the name endings. As in our study we only considered the last character and not the n-gram of endings like bigram or trigram of name endings, we see a potential of improvement if we consider n-grams too.
- A dictionary based approach can be considered for common Nepali names for fast inference and accurate results.

8 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study addressed the significant gap in gender classification research for low-resource language Nepali, specifically focusing on names written in the Devanagari Scrip. Moreover, the research focus on comparing the performance of traditional machine learning algorithms and advanced contextualized transformer architectures, specifically fine-tuned variants of BERT, for gender classification in Nepali names. Utilizing an imbalanced dataset with class weights assigned to handle the disparity between the majority and minority classes, the study discovered that DeBERTa outperformed other models in the task, followed closely by DistilBERT. Among traditional algorithms, Random Forest proved to be the most successful.

Although these findings offer meaningful contributions to gender classification in the Nepali linguistic landscape, further research remains necessary to explore the role of middle names, n-grams of name endings, and dictionary-based approaches for fast and efficient inference. Continuous advancements in reliable gender detection will undoubtedly promote more inclusive and unbiased AI services, ensuring fairness and equality in diverse applications.

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